

Perceived Effect of Climate Change on Poultry Feed Prices among Poultry Farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria
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ABSTRACT

The study determined the level of perceived effect of climate change on poultry feed prices (PFPs), adaptation strategies used by the respondents during hike in the PFPs and the level of respondents' awareness to climate change effect on poultry production. Interview schedule was used to collect data with percentages; means and standard deviation, while inferential were used to test for hypotheses. Results show that timely rainfall ($\bar{x}=3.42$) ranked highest of all the perceived effect variables, while more than half (57.4%) of the respondents had a negative perceived effect of climate change on poultry feed price. Further results show that reduced labour cost ($\bar{x}=2.35$) ranked highest of all the adaptation strategies used during a hike in the price of poultry feed. Majority (70.4%) of the respondents indicated a high level of awareness of climate change's effect on the poultry feed prices. Further results show that years of experience in poultry ($\beta= -0.540$; $r=0.00$) had a significant relationship at $p \leq 0.01$ with the effect of climate change on poultry feed price. The study suggests the adequate usage of e-extension technologies that will provide adequate information on climate variability to help the farmers predict on when and when not to produce to prevent low productivity.

Keywords: *Climate change, e-extension, poultry feed price.*

INTRODUCTION

Chicken meat and eggs, the most important sources of animal protein, are produced in backyard coops, which have been important and beneficial over the world (Nawab, *et al.*, 2018). It is characterized by a number of elements, such as the usage of a local night shelter, scavenging techniques, natural chick hatching, and low bird productivity. In rural areas, raising backyard poultry is common and mostly uses unimpressive local chicken breeds. These chickens are also referred to as "rural," "backyard," "indigenous," "scavenging," "traditional," "local," "native," or "family" chickens depending on the local language (Sheikh *et al.*, 2018). Rural backyard poultry farming encourages self-employment and provides protein-rich, reasonably priced food as supplemental income.

In some parts of the world, poultry farming dominates the livestock industry when compared to other sectors. This occurs as a result of the expansion in global population and the spread of urbanization, which is driving up demand for animal products, most notably chicken (FAO, 2025). Climate change has a severe negative impact on the expansion of the poultry business globally and may shift the source of chicken protein to other available and affordable sources of protein. According to Nyoni *et al.* (2019), issues with backyard poultry production, like poor growth rates and low egg output, may be exacerbated by or directly influenced by a changing environment. Extreme temperatures and humidity, in particular, put birds under a lot of stress and impair their performance.

Heat stress harms the physiological, immune, and digestive health of poultry birds, which ultimately causes the poultry business to suffer significant financial losses (Liverpool *et al.*, 2019). This is due to the limited tolerance of chicken genotypes for high temperatures. The effects of heat stress on the birds' egg production, quality, size, and weight loss have a negative impact on backyard poultry farming's ability to provide meat (Nkukwana, 2018).

In many rural parts of Africa, poultry production constitutes an important agricultural activity, with most farmers typically relying on locally available resources for management and production. Despite previously being ignored, home food security has recently received significant attention due to its significant contribution to poverty reduction. It provides opportunities for off-farm employment and income generation, as well as a source of donations and religious sacrifices (Sonaiya, 2019).

Poultry production by smallholders is viewed as a source of income compatible with the idea of small-scale agricultural development. Furthermore, the smallholder chicken production systems are not constrained by land, a crucial production resource in rural areas. Products made from village chicken are frequently one of the primary animal protein sources for low-income households. Children under five who are ill or malnourished can get high-quality protein from eggs (Weaver, 2019). Because chickens are smaller and reproduce more quickly than other livestock and they are more frequently butchered and consumed within the family (Delgado *et al.*, 2019). Given the vast advantages in poultry production, the advancement in information and communication

technologies (ICT's) should provide opportunity to poultry farmers to harness and utilise information and knowledge so as to improve in their productivity that could be enhanced through the use of electronic extension (e-extension) (Anyoha *et al.*, 2018).

The value of backyard poultry to rural farming households and their sheer volume has been an important instrument in reducing the impact of poverty syndrome in rural areas. Rural poultry is significant and adds to the human population's protein needs. Therefore, the importance of rural poultry production in the nation's supply of hens and eggs cannot be overstated. Due to the poultry's remarkable physiological adaptability, poultry farming is feasible in various agro-climate environments (National Commission on Agriculture [NCA], 2018). Poultry farming is profitable in rural and urban regions due to its small space requirements, inexpensive initial investment, quick return on investment, and evenly distributed turn over throughout the year (FAO, 2025).

However, one of the main issues influencing agricultural production of both crops and livestock, including crop losses, low agricultural productivity, and low turnout, is climate change, which deals with the statistical distribution of weather. (Tegene and Tiruneh, 2018). Typically, this relates to fluctuations in climatic factors, including temperature, precipitation, wind, and humidity. The earth's natural environment is subject to climate change, which results from interactions between the atmosphere, ocean, and land, as well as variations in the amount of solar energy that reaches the planet. A greenhouse effect is created when certain gases, such as water vapour and carbon dioxide, trap heat in the atmosphere. Burning fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas is one example of an activity carried out by humans that contributes to climate change (Gbetibouo, 2019). Additionally, he stated that the observed rise in human activity is most likely to blame for the observed increase in the average world temperature. The term "global warming" often refers to this occurrence. Abioja and Abiona (2021), stated that major factor affecting agricultural productivity is climate change. It frequently has a negative impact on poultry feed prices which has caused rural farmers to seriously worry and consequently impacted productivity for chicken goods. On this ground, many findings have been made on climate change, but there is little empirical evidence on the effect of climate change on poultry feed price, hence, this study.

The main objective of the study is to assess the effect of climate change on poultry feed price in Ondo State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives were to:

1. determine the socio-economic characteristics of the poultry farmers;
2. identify adaptation strategies used by the poultry farmers during hike in (PFPs);
3. determine the level of respondent's awareness to climate change effect (s) on PFPs hike in the study area and
4. determine the level of perceived effect of climate change on PFPs among the respondents.

The research hypothesis (H₀) states that, there is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and the effect of climate change on poultry feed prices

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out between February and June 2021 in Ondo State. The state is made up of 18 Local Government Areas and lies between longitudes 4°30' and 6° East of the Greenwich Meridian, 5°45' and 8°15' North of the Equator (Ondo State Ministry of Economic Planning and Budget, 2025). It is bounded in the North by Ekiti State; in the East by Edo State; in the West by Oyo and Ogun States, and in the South by the Atlantic Ocean. Respondents were chosen using a multistage sampling process. In the first stage, three of the State's eighteen Local Government Areas (LGAs), Ondo East, Ondo West, and Akure South, were conveniently chosen due to their potentials for tourism. In the second stage, four communities from each of the LGAs were chosen purposively based on the abundance of poultry production to make a total of twelve (12) communities. At the final stage, ten (10) poultry farmers were chosen using a snowball procedure to give a total of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents for the study. To obtain pertinent quantitative information on the adaptation strategies used by the respondents, the perceived impact of climate change on the poultry feed price the respondents' strategies for coping with increases in the price of poultry feed, and the respondents' awareness of the effects of climate change on poultry production, a structured interview schedule was used. In order to make appropriate conclusions about the hypothesis at both the 0.01 and 0.05 level of confidence, multiple regression model (MRM) and correlation were used to summarize the data collected using percentages, means, and standard deviations. The dependent variable for this study was the poultry feed price, which its perception was operationalized and measured using 5-point Likert-type scale of 'SA'=Strongly agreed (5), 'A'=Agreed (4), 'U'=Undecided (3), 'D'=Disagreed (2) and 'SD'=Strongly

disagreed (1). Respondents' choices were summed up to obtain the perceived effect score. Perceived effect was categorized into positive or negative using mean, plus or minus standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents (Table 1) shows that females (53.3%) participate in poultry farming than male (46.7%), suggesting that poultry farming is an accessible livelihood option, particularly because it can be combined with household responsibilities. A large proportion of the respondents were married, indicating that poultry production plays an important role in supporting household income and family welfare. The dominance of the Yoruba ethnic group reflects the location of the study area in southwestern Nigeria. Most respondents depended on family and friends as their main source of credit, which points to limited access to formal financial institutions and may

restrict farm expansion and investment in improved technologies (Afolayan et al., 2021). More than half of the respondents had no contact with extension agents, highlighting a major weakness in agricultural information delivery, which can negatively affect productivity and management practices (Anderson & Feder, 2007). Mean age of the respondent (= 42.9 years) reveals that poultry farming is practiced mostly by those within the economically active age group, with the ability to manage the farms effectively. The mean size of the households indicates that there is a dependence on families as a source of labor that may limit farm income. Despite this and adequate farming experience, low incomes and small numbers of stock holdings indicate that poultry production is still done on a small scale and therefore there is a need for institutional support to enhance productivity and commercialization (World Bank, 2020).

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
Sex			
Male	56	46.7	
Female	64	53.3	
Total	120	100.0	
Marital Status			
Single	41	34.2	
Married	67	55.8	
Divorced	7	5.8	
Widowed	5	4.2	
Total	120	100.0	
Ethnicity			
Yoruba	100	83.3	
Igbo	20	16.7	
Total	120	100.0	
Religion			
Christianity	96	80.0	
Islam	20	16.7	
Traditional	4	3.3	
Total	120	100.0	
Source of Credit			
Family and friends	89	74.2	
Money lender	14	11.7	
Microfinance	17	14.1	
Total	120	100.0	
Access to Extension Contact			
Yes	52	43.3	
No	68	56.7	
Total	120	100.0	
Age			
0-20	4	3.3	
21-40	60	50.0	
41-60	40	33.3	
61-80	15	12.5	

81-100	1	0.9	
Total	120	100.0	42.9 (±13.8)
Household Size			
0-10	109	90.8	
11-20	9	7.5	
21-30	1	0.9	
> 30	1	0.9	
Total	120	100.0	6.6 (±3.1)
Years of Experience			
0-20	103	85.8	
21-40	15	12.5	
41-60	2	1.7	
Total	120	100.0	11.2 (±6.4)
Annual income from Poultry			
1000-1,000,000	110	91.8	
1,000,000-2,000,000	4	3.3	
2,000,000-3,000,000	1	0.9	
3,000,000-4,000,000	1	0.9	
4,000,000-5,000,000	4	3.3	
Total	120	100.0	₦921,300 (±410,600)
Total number of Stock			
50-3000	102	94.4	
3001-6000	4	16.7	
6001& above	2	1.9	
Total	120	100.0	2,150 (±1,120)

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Adaptation strategies used during hike in PFPs

The data indicated in Table 2 reveal that farmers adopt different strategies in order to deal with an increase in the prices of poultry food. Reduction in the cost of labour, which emerged with a high percentage of 82.2%, indicates that farmers mainly react to short-term changes in variable costs. This practice is common with poultry farmers operating on a smaller scale because a higher amount of their production costs relates to labour. Reducing the labour force ensures a way to compensate for an increase in the prices of poultry feeds (Afolayan et al., 2021). Another key strategy is to raise the price of poultry commodities like chickens and eggs by a percentage of 76.6%. This is a form of cost transfer, whereby farmers raise the price of their commodities to meet the increased production costs. Similar findings were obtained by Ojo and Adebayo (2020), whereby poultry farmers were found to adjust their production price in response to increased production costs, especially during times of high demands. Feed rationing, which consisted of 61.9% of the responses, included reducing the amount of feed given to the birds. Even though such a strategy might reduce the amount spent on feeds in the short run, it might have potential drawbacks with regards to growth and performance (Abioja & Abiona, 2021). Rationing the use of food, which consisted of 50.1% of the responses, to supplement poultry feed clearly

indicates the use of alternative sources of food to reduce the amount spent on poultry feed costs.

The use of the Free-Range system (46.2%) shows that farmers have transformed from intensive systems to semi-intensive or extensive production systems that allow chickens to scavenge for food in search of nutrient intake. However, the system has the potential to increase the risk of disease infection and production (Oladeebo & Ambe-Lamidi, 2020). Similarly, the management practice of downgrading feed quality while keeping the quantity the same (43.1%) shows the desire to utilize less expensive feed formulations, which consequently has the potential to affect production efficiency. The use of locally formulated feed instead of importing feed (38.6%) indicated an increasing recognition of the available local feed sources for economic reasons. The formulation of local feed is strongly recommended as a long-term strategy for making the industry less dependent on imported feed ingredients, thus improving the ability of the industry to withstand market disturbances (Ajayi et al., 2022). The strategy that was observed least often was the administration of excess water compared to feed (30.4%), which was most likely done periodically in order to manage feed intake as a way of combating heat stress. The findings confirm Abioja & Abiona (2021) which observed that the administration of enough water reduces stress

associated with harsh environments as well as feed shortages. The above findings show that the poultry farmers are mainly using short-run adaptation approaches centered on minimizing costs rather than

the use of structural adaptation approaches. This trait shows the susceptibility of the poultry production systems to changes in the price of feed and the need for support to develop adaptive mechanisms.

Table 2: Adaptation strategies used during hike in (PFPs)

Adaptation Strategies*	percentage (n=120)
Reduced labour cost	82.2
Increased price of poultry product	76.6
Level of feed given to poultry birds is reduced (rationing)	61.9
Use of food remains to supplement poultry feed	50.1
Practice free range system	46.2
Feed quality is reduced but quantity is constant	43.1
Introduction of locally formulated feed instead of imported feed	38.6
Introduction of more water than feeds to the birds	30.4

Source: Field survey, 2024.

*Multiple responses

Perception of the poultry farmers towards the effect of climate change on PFPs

Table 3 show that respondents agreed that herder farmer crisis due to open grazing on cereal crops increases poultry feed price (\bar{x} =3.52), high relative humidity increase the rate of disease infestation which in-turn increases the cost of production for feed formulation (\bar{x} =3.41) drought destroys crops production for poultry feed formulation (\bar{x} =3.36), high wind intensity destroys pollination of maize and other cereals which in-turn lead to hike in price of poultry feed (\bar{x} =3.24). On the other hand, respondents disagreed that timely rainfall helps the production of grains for poultry feed formulation which in-turn reduces poultry feed price (\bar{x} =3.43),

water intake is more during sunny climate which also influences feed intake (\bar{x} =3.20), availability of poultry feed during cold climate lowers feed price (\bar{x} =3.19), poultry birds don't feed well during cold climate which lowers the rate of feed intake per bird (\bar{x} =3.13). Figure 1 shows that the majority (69.4%) of the respondents had negative perception towards the effect of climate change on poultry feed price while 30.6% indicated positive perception, meaning that the farmers perceive that the climate change has more adverse effect than positive effect on poultry feed price. This corroborates the findings of Tiruneh & Tegene (2018) that increased global temperature; extreme weather conditions lead to decrease in the rate of poultry feed consumption.

Table 3: Perception of the poultry farmers towards the effect of climate change (PFPs)

Perception statements	Mean (n=120)
Herder farmer crisis due to open grazing on cereal crops increases poultry feed price	3.52
Timely rainfall helps the production of grains for poultry feed formulation which in-turn reduces poultry feed price	3.43
High relative humidity increase the rate of disease infestation which in-turn increases the cost of production for feed formulation	3.41
Lengthen drought destroys the production of crops for poultry feed formulation	3.36
High wind intensity destroys pollination of maize and other cereals which in-turn lead to hike in price of poultry feed	3.24
Water intake is more during sunny climate which also influences feed intake	3.20
Poultry feed is readily available during cold climate which lowers the feed price	3.19
Poultry birds don't feed well during cold climate which lowers the rate of feed intake per bird	3.13

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Figure 1: Perception of the respondents towards the effect of climate change on (PFPs)

Respondent’s awareness to climate change effect on poultry production

Result in Table 4 shows that climate change may result in death of birds, particularly chicks and layers (\bar{x} =2.46) ranked the highest of all the awareness statement followed by climate change affects reproductive capacity in poultry (\bar{x} =2.37), hot weather causes heat stress in poultry (\bar{x} =2.31) high temperature reduces fertility and hatchability in breeder birds (\bar{x} =2.30), High temperature decreases

heat periods in animals (\bar{x} =2.29), while climate changes affects stocking density (\bar{x} =1.60) ranked the least. The grand mean is 2.22. This implies that majority of the respondents are occasionally aware of the effect of climate change on poultry production. This affirms the submission of Tiruneh & Tegene (2018) that climate change impacts poultry production by imposing stress on the homeostasis in the birds.

Table 4: Farmers’ awareness to climate change effect on poultry production

Awareness	Mean (n=120)
Climate change may result in death of birds, particularly chicks and layers	2.46
Climate change affects reproductive capacity in poultry	2.37
Hot weather causes heat stress in poultry	2.31
High temperature reduces fertility and hatchability in breeder birds	2.30
High temperature decreases heat periods in animals	2.29
Climate change affects stocking density	1.60

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Constraints militating against rural poultry production

The Results in Table 5 show that diseases outbreak (\bar{x} =1.78) ranked the highest constraint militating against the poultry farmers followed by low income generated (\bar{x} =1.69), poor access to veterinary doctor (\bar{x} =1.67), frequent climate change (\bar{x} =1.66), poor marketing especially during glut (\bar{x} =1.63), Poor transportation (\bar{x} =1.61) and low quality of products (\bar{x} = 1.60) ranked the least constraint militating

against rural poultry farmers in the study area. The grand mean is 1.66. This implies that majority of the respondents indicated a major constraint. The results put together show that rural poultry farmers are faced with a web of health, economic, infrastructural, and climate-related challenges, hence the need for coordinated solutions-straightforward veterinary support, improvement in market development aspects, and climate-resilient farming approaches.

Table 5: Constraints militating against rural poultry production

Constraints	Mean (n=120)
Diseases outbreak	1.78
Low income generated	1.69
Poor access to veterinary doctor	1.67
Frequent climate change	1.66
poor marketing especially during glut	1.63
Poor transportation	1.61
Low quality of products	1.60

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Relationship between socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and the effect of climate change on poultry feed prices

Results of correlation analysis in Table 6 show that there was a positive and significant relationship between perceived effect of climate change on PFPs and household size ($r=0.03$), experience in poultry ($r=0.00$) and number of stocks ($r=0.03$) of the respondents at $P \leq 0.01$. This implies that household size; year of experience in poultry and credit source all have influence on the effect of climate change on PFPs in the study area. On the other hand, results in Table 7 show the standardized co-efficient for household size ($\beta=0.329$), years of experience in

poultry ($\beta= -0.540$) and source of credit ($\beta= -0.207$) had significant relationship and equally flagged as significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance with the R^2 value of 0.655. This divulges that the personal characteristics cumulatively contribute 65.5percent in influencing the effect of climate change on PFPs. This implies that the respondents could have possibly make use of his increased household size as source of labour so as to reduce cost. Similarly, with increase in years of experience in poultry, the respondents would have acquired a lot of skills that would help to cushion the effect of climate change on PFPs so also, source of credit.

Table 6: Relationship between socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and the effect of climate change on PFPs

Socio-economic Variables	r-value
Household Size	0.689*
Years of Experience in poultry	0.993**
Number of Stocks	0.612*

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 7: Relationship between socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and the effect of climate change on PFPs

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	20.306	1.489		13.637
Age	.009	.024	.063	.363
Gender	.608	.481	.132	1.265
Marital status	.265	.357	.088	.742
Ethnicity	-.126	.601	-.020	-.209
Religion	.356	.466	.079	.764
household size	.170	.078	.329	2.180
years of exp. in poultry	-.121	.042	-.540	-2.849
access to extension contact	-.235	.488	-.051	-.481
source of credit	-.658	.315	-.207	-2.089
estimated annual income from poultry	2.069E-007	.000	.082	.465
annual income from other enterprise	2.002E-007	.000	.073	.645
total number of stock	1.261E-	.000	.012	.070

Source: Field survey, 2024.
R²=0.655; **F**=61.182

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The poultry farmers indicated reduced labour cost as the adaptation strategy used during the hike in the price of poultry feed. Also, the majority of the respondents had a negative perception towards the effect of climate change on poultry feed price, while diseases outbreak, low income generated, poor access to the veterinary doctors, frequent climate change, poor marketing, especially during glut and poor transportation were the major constraints identified.

In order to assist farmers in forecasting when and when not to produce in order to avoid low productivity, which in turn has an impact on the price of chicken feed in Nigeria. Government, together

with other key stakeholders, should encourage the use of locally developed poultry feed formulations to make the production of poultry cheaper and less reliant on imports. Additionally, credit services from cooperatives and micro-financial organizations should be scaled up to help farmers expand their businesses and adopt better technologies. Improvement of infrastructure in the rural areas, as well as the development of marketing channels, should be done to counter losses that occur after production as well as make the prices of poultry stable. Secondly, policies for small-scale poultry farmers should be the priority to make poultry production sustainable.

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